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Assessment Of Water Portability In Male And Female Hostel Borehole In Abdu Gusau Polytechnic Talata mafara, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research work investigated the portability of borehole water consumed by male and female students in their respective hostels in Abdu gusau polytechnic talata mafara zamfara state. Bi weekly sample collection and laboratory analysis were adopted for two month period (August and September) by 8:00AM to 12:00PM all the times. All the parameters were tested using standard methods, SPSS version 20.0. The results showed that, pH level for in male hostel was 8.38 ± 0.74 , and that of female hostel was 8.50 ± 0.54 as compared to WHO recommended limits (6.5-8.5). The electrical conductivity recorded $187.63 \pm 100.00 \mu\text{s}$ for male hostel, and $121.00 \pm 83.07 \mu\text{s}$ for the female hostel as against that of the WHO recommended limit ($500 \mu\text{s}$). The water temperature was $26.50 \pm 2.78 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $28.75 \pm 2.92 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for male and female hostel respectively as compared to $25\text{-}30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ recommended by WHO standard. BOD showcased $4.88 \pm 10.27 \text{ mg/l}$ for male hostel and $10.75 \pm 1.39 \text{ mg/l}$ for female hostel as against to 5.0 mg/l set up by WHO recommendation limit. Turbidity in male hostel was $0.00 \pm 0.00 \text{ NTU}$ and that of the female hostel was $0.13 \pm 0.35 \text{ NTU}$ as opposed to 5.0 NTU recommended by the WHO. DO level in the male hostel was $7.63 \pm 15.60 \text{ mg/l}$, while that of the female hostel's borehole was $2.00 \pm 1.93 \text{ mg/l}$ as compared to that of the WHO standard ($5.0\text{-}10.0 \text{ mg/l}$). TDS in male student hostel's borehole water sample was $0.55 \pm 1.40 \text{ mg/l}$, and that in the female hostel's borehole showed $0.88 \pm 1.73 \text{ mg/l}$ as compared to the WHO set up limit ($250\text{-}500 \text{ mg/l}$). TSS concentration showed $0.90 \pm 0.84 \text{ mg/l}$ and $0.75 \pm 0.71 \text{ mg/l}$ for male and female hostel's borehole respectively. The coliform detected in MPN index/100ml was 1.81 ± 0.18 and 2.21 ± 0.00 for male and female hostel's borehole respectively as compared to $0.00 \text{ MPN index/100ml}$ recommended by WHO standard. Therefore the water need proper treatment before consumption. Hence more research are needed.

Keywords: Borehole water, portability evaluation, Abdu Gusau Polytechnic Student, Student's hostels

INTRODUCTION

Borehole water is commonly believed to be pure and safe to drink (Odeyemi *et al.*, 2024). Access to potable water is a fundamental human need and it is therefore, a basic human right. Potable water is that which possesses the quality that renders it fit and safe for drinking (Abdulsalam and Sule, 2020).

In Nigeria, over 120 million peoples use boreholes as their main source of drinking water. (Musa *et al.*, 2023). Borehole and well are the main sources of water for residents of Rivers state known to be rich in crude oil deposit which predisposes both water sources to possible contamination with heavy and non-heavy metals with attendant health implications (Ngozi *et al.*, 2020).

Water plays a vital role in the existence of life and various sector of the economy such as agriculture, livestock production, forestry, industrial power generation, fisheries and other creative activities (Mayosore & Madaka, 2020). Water needs to be available at almost every moment of existence but the availability of water in space and time is limited by environmental factors such as climate, geography of an area and physical conditions (Ugwoha and Nwike, 2018).

Environmental pollution is increasingly becoming a major global problem (Adesina *et al.*, 2024). Some of the physicochemical characteristics of water are temperature, salinity, light penetration, pH, biological oxygen demand (BOD), dissolved oxygen (DO), total dissolved solids (TDS), total suspended solids (TSS), and nutrients like nitrite and phosphate (Rahman *et al.*, 2023).

The excellence of Fresh water can simply affect by the Waste disposal, anthropogenic-induced changes and Seasonal Variations, which lead various negative features to the living welfare. This constant disintegration of fresh water, its needs to be protected from further deterioration by regularly monitoring and evaluating the water and its qualities (Manonmani *et al.*, 2024).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Abdu Gusau Polytechnic is a state government polytechnic located in Talata Mafara, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Polytechnic was Established 1992 by Yahaya Abdulkarim as he signed a bill that established the 'Talata Mafara Polythecnic'. The Sokoto state government renamed the Polytechnic to 'Abdu Gusau Polytechnic' in February, 1995. This was done in honor of the late engineer Abdu Gusau who died in November, 1994, in recognition of his contribution to the development of the State (History/agpmafara.edu.ng, 2020). Zamfara state of Nigeria was created by a Federal decree in 1996, (NIPC, 2019 and Alapiki & Henry, 2005). And this necessitated the relocation of the polytechnic to a new permanent site in Talata Mafara. The Sokoto state government was no longer responsible for it, and it wasn't legally possible to have an institution belonging to Zamfara state located in Sokoto. It's now located Talata Mafara, Zamfara State, Nigeria at coordinate 12.56079°N 6.07938°E.

Sample collection

Bi-weekly sample collection of the water samples were maintained for the period of Four months (August & September- 2024). Samples were collected from two bore hole each in both male and female hostels. 8:30 AM to 12:30 PM is the time, period in which the sample collection was maintained. The water samples were transported immediately to laboratory for analysis. The sampling method was adopted from (Robert, 2012).

Physicochemical parameters

- Biweekly determination of water temperature, pH, TDS, TSS, TS, conductivity (using conductivity meter with model no. **(DDS307W)**). Adopted from Abdulkadir *et al.* (2013).
- Water turbidity was measured using the guideline provided by water action voluntiers (WAV, 2008).
- DO and BOD were measured in line with the instructions provided in DO Meter (model no: **INE-JPSJ-605F**).
- The physicochemical parameters of the water were analysed using the procedures described in internationally approved practical hand book of soil, water and air analysis published by Gupta. (2014) and UWW, (2018).

Biological parameters

Most probable number (MPN) techniques was used to assess the coliform count in the water sample taking into account the principle of Thomas equation for the evaluation of coliform count in the portability of water.

Assessment and Evaluation of the portability of the borehole water in male and female hostels Abdu Gusau Polytechnic Talata mafara

The portability of the borehole water in male and female hostel was achieved by comparing the values of the test parameters with those of the WHO set up limits, as adopted from Ngozi *et al.*, 2020 and Odeyemi *et al.*, 2023.

Data Analysis

k) With the aid of Statistical Package of Social Science (SPSS) Version 20.0, one way ANOVA, was used to study the mean variation in the water physicochemical and Biological parameters.

l) Karl Pearson's equation correlation was used to assess the relationship between the physicochemical parameters.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.0 Results

The result of physicochemical and biological parameters of borehole water collected from Abdu Gusau polytechnic male and female hostels with comparison to WHO recommended limits for the portability of water were presented below.

4.1 Physicochemical Parameters concentrations in Male and female hostel Abdu Gusau Polytechnic Talata mafara.

Table 1 presents the results of the water's physicochemical parameters concentrations in Male female hostel's borehole water. pH was 8.42 ± 0.58 , Water temperature was 27.67 ± 2.74 , Conductivity was 155.88 ± 87.73 , Dissolved Oxygen was 5.00 ± 10.70 , Biological Oxygen Demand was 2.92 ± 7.00 , Turbidity was 0.04 ± 0.20 , Total Dissolved Solid was 0.81 ± 1.83 and Total Suspended Solid was 0.72 ± 0.76 .

4.2 Physicochemical Parameters Concentrations in Male and Female hostel in AGP Talata mafara with Sampling Months

Table 2 displays the average monthly values of the Bakolori Dam's physicochemical characteristics. Notably, there were significant differences in TDS ($p = 0.0270$), TSS ($p = 0.0200$), and Coliform ($p = 0.030$) between the sampling months. Water temperature was found to be highest in September, with Conductivity found to be lowest in August, while turbidity was found to be highest in August, and water turbidity was found to be lower value in September but higher in August. Highest values of Water pH, DO, and BOD were recorded in August.

4.3 Physicochemical and Biological Parameters Concentrations in in AGP male and female hostels according to the hostels

In table 3, Physicochemical parameter values were compared between sampling sites and no significant differences were found for any of the parameters ($p > 0.05$). The lowest value of water temperature was recorded in the male hostel, but the highest value observed in female hostel. DO and BOD were found to be lowest in the Female hostel with highest value recorded in the male hostel, the lowest value of TDS was recorded in male hostel, TSS value was found to be highest in the male hostel, and water turbidity was found to be lowest value in the male hostel but highest value in the female hostel.

4.4 Correlation coefficient of Physicochemical and biological Parameters in male and students borehole water

Table 4 shows relationship between different physicochemical parameters in Abdu Gusau polytechnic male and female students' boreholes. A very strong positive correlation was found between TDS and pH ($r = 0.565$), DO and BOD (0.706), and BOD and temperature (0.683). A very strong negative correlation was found between TDS and temperature (-0.635), while a very strong positive correlation was found between pH and DO (0.648) and BOD (0.659). Coliform showed very strong positive correlation with TDS, Temperature, and BOD, So also strong positive correlation between coliform and TSS was observed, but very strong negative correlation observed between coliform and DO.

4.5 Evaluation of the quality of male and female hostel's borehole water in line with WHO recommended limits for the assessment of it portability.

The table 5 below showed that, pH, level for in male hostel was 8.38 ± 0.74 , and that of female hostel was 8.50 ± 0.54 as compared to WHO recommended limits ($6.5-8.5$). The electrical conductivity recorded $187.63 \pm 100.00 \mu\text{s}$ for male hostel, and $121.00 \pm 83.07 \mu\text{s}$ for the female hostel as against that of the WHO recommended limit ($500 \mu\text{s}$). The water temperature was $26.50 \pm 2.78 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $28.75 \pm 2.92 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for male and female hostel respectively as compared to $25-30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ recommended by WHO standard. BOD showcased $4.88 \pm 10.27 \text{ mg/l}$ for male hostel and $10.75 \pm 1.39 \text{ mg/l}$ for female hostel as against to 5.0 mg/l set up by

WHO recommendation limit. Turbidity in male hostel was 0.00 ± 0.00 NTU and that of the female hostel was 0.13 ± 0.35 NTU as opposed to 5.0 NTU recommended by the WHO. DO level in the male hostel was 7.63 ± 15.60 mg/l, while that of the female hostel's borehole was 2.00 ± 1.93 mg/l as compared to that of the WHO standard (5.0-10.0 mg/l). TDS in male student hostel's borehole water sample was 0.55 ± 1.40 mg/l, and that in the female hostel's borehole showed 0.88 ± 1.73 mg/l as compared to the WHO set up limit (250-500 mg/l). TSS concentration showed 0.90 ± 0.84 mg/l and 0.75 ± 0.71 mg/l for male and female hostel's borehole respectively. The coliform detected in MPN index/100ml was 1.81 ± 0.18 and 2.21 ± 0.00 for male and female hostel's borehole respectively as compared to 0.00 MPN index/100ml recommended by WHO standard.

Table 1. Overall Physicochemical and Biological Parameters Concentrations in Abdu gusau polytechnic talata mafara student hostels

Parameters	Mean±S.D	Range Values	
		Minimum	Maximum
pH	8.42±0.58	8.00	10.00
Water Temp. (°C)	27.67±2.75	22.00	34.00
Conductivity (µS)	155.88±87.73	65.00	323.00
DO (mg/l)	5.00±10.70	0.00	46.00
BOD (mg/l)	2.92±7.00	0.00	30.00
Turbidity (NTU)	0.04±0.20	0.00	1.00
TDS (mg/l)	0.81±1.84	0.00	7.00
TSS (mg/l)	0.72±0.76	0.00	2.00
Coliform index/100ml) (MPN)	1.98±0.81	0.13	2.21

Key: pH= power of hydrogen, °C= Degree celcius, µS = Micro siemon, mg/l = Milligram per litre, DO = Dissolved Oxysgen, BOD = Biological Oxygen Demand, NTU= Nuphelometric Turbidity Unit, cm= Centimeter, TDS= Total Dissolved Solid, TSS= Total Suspended Solid, TS= Total Solid.

Table 2. Mean Monthly Physicochemical and Biological Parameters Concentrations in Abdu gusau polytechnic talata mafara student hostels

Parameter	August	September	P-Value
pH	8.00±0.00	8.33±0.52	0.14
Water Temp. (°C)	28.17±0.75	29.33±0.52	0.16
Conductivity (µS)	103.50±65.10	192.00±70.15	0.34
DO (mg/l)	0.500±0.55	1.17±0.98	0.12
BOD (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.33±0.82	0.14
Turbidity (NTU)	0.17±0.41	0.00±0.00	0.41
TDS (mg/l)	0.23±0.41	0.00±0.00	0.03
TSS (mg/l)	1.70±0.79	0.33±0.52	0.02
Coliform (MPN Index/100ml)	1.89±0.99	1.63±0.95	0,03

Key: pH= power of hydrogen, °C= Degree celcius, µS = Micro siemon, mg/l = Milligram per litre, DO = Dissolved Oxysgen, BOD = Biological Oxygen Demand, NTU= Nuphelometric Turbidity Unit, cm= Centimeter, TDS= Total Dissolved Solid, TSS= Total Suspended Solid, TS= Total Solid, (P≤0.05).

Table 3. Physicochemical and Biological parameters in Abdu Gusau polytechnic talata mafara student hostels

Parameter	Male Hostel	Female Hostel	P-value
pH	8.38±0.74	8.50±0.54	0.90
Water Temp. (°C)	26.50±2.78	28.75±2.92	0.27
Conductivity (µS)	187.63±100.00	121.00±83.07	0.33
DO (mg/l)	7.63±15.60	2.00±1.93	0.59
BOD (mg/l)	4.88±10.27	0.75±1.39	0.52
Turbidity (NTU)	0.00±0.00	0.13±0.35	0.39
TDS (mg/l)	0.55±1.40	0.88±1.73	0.89
TSS (mg/l)	0.90±0.84	0.75±0.71	0.59
Coliform	1.81±0.18	2. 21±0.00	1.59±0.89

Key: pH= power of hydrogen, °C= Degree celcius, µS = Micro siemon, mg/l = Milligram per litre, DO = Dissolved Oxysgen, BOD = Biological Oxygen Demand, NTU= Nuphelometric Turbidity Unit, cm= Centimeter, TDS= Total Dissolved Solid, TSS= Total Suspended Solid, TS= Total Solid, (P≤0.05).

Table 4. Correlation Coefficient of Physicochemical and Biological Parameters in Abdu gusau polytechnic talata mafara student hostels

	TDS	TSS	Turbidity	Conductivity	pH	Temp.	DO	BOD (mg/l)
TSS (mg/l)	-0.139							
Turbidity (NTU)	-0.094	0.080						
Conductivity (µS)	0.078	-0.407	-0.179					
pH	0.565**	-0.115	-0.152	0.122				
Temp. (°C)	-0.635**	-0.194	0.026	-0.169	-0.398			
DO (mg/l)	0.706**	0.167	-0.080	-0.114	0.648**	-0.551		
BOD (mg/l)	0.683**	0.163	-0.089	-0.092	0.659**	-0.550	0.994	
Coliform (MPN Index/100ml)	0.467**	0.857*	0.564	0.113	0.431	0.571**	-0.831**	0.983**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 5. Comparison of the Physicochemical and Biological parameters Parameters in Abdu gusau polytechnic talata mafara student hostels with WHO standard

Parameter	Male Hostel	Female Hostel	WHO standard	Comment
pH	8.38±0.74	8.50±0.54	6.5-8.5	MWL,FWL
Water Temp. (°C)	26.50±2.78	28.75±2.92	25-30	MWL,FWL
Conductivity (µS)	187.63±100.00	121.00±83.07	500	MWL,FWL
DO (mg/l)	7.63±15.60	2.00±1.93	5.0-10.0	MAL,FBL
BOD (mg/l)	4.88±10.27	0.75±1.39	5.0	MWL,FWL
Turbidity (NTU)	0.00±0.00	0.13±0.35	5	MWL,FWL
TDS (mg/l)	0.55±1.40	0.88±1.73	250-500	MBL,FBL
TSS (mg/l)	0.90±0.84	0.75±0.71	1000	MBL,FBL
Coliform	1.81±0.18	2. 21±0.00	0.0	MAL,FAL

Key = MAL (Male hostel value is Above WHO recommended limit), FAL (Female hostel value is Above WHO recommended limit), MWL (Male hostel value is Within WHO recommended limit), FWL (Female hostel value is Within WHO recommended limit), MBL (Male hostel value is Below WHO recommended limit) and FBL (Female hostel value is Below WHO recommended limit).

Figure 1. Bar chat illustrating the comparison between the physicochemical and biological parameters in male and female student’s hostel from Abdu Gusau Polytechnic with WHO set up recommended limits

DISCUSSION

The fact that, pH, level for in male hostel was 8.38 ± 0.74 , and that of female hostel was 8.50 ± 0.54 as compared to WHO recommended limits (6.5-8.5). The results showed that, the Ph level for the borehole from the both hostels were within the WHO limit, hence no obvious deterioration in the water regarding the acidity or alkalinity concentration. Similar finding reported from portharcort Nigeria by Ngozi *et al.*, 2020, but different case Borno state Nigeria by Musa *et al.*, 2023, also similar finding from Chad public school's borehole water by Abdoulaye *et al.*, 2022, and different findings from Katsina state's borehole water by Madaka, 2020 and Choba campus portharcourt by Ugwoha and Nwike 2018. The electrical conductivity recorded $187.63 \pm 100.00 \mu\text{s}$ for male hostel, and $121.00 \pm 83.07 \mu\text{s}$ for the female hostel as against that of the WHO recommended limit ($500 \mu\text{s}$), this means that the water from two hostels are within the portability limit by WHO, hence no obvious pollution in this regard. Many studies recorded similar findings from their borehole water, among of which are Abdulsalam and Sule 2020 from Ilorin kwara state Nigeria, Odeyemi *et al.*, 2023 from Ado Ekiti, Ekiti state Nigeria. The water temperature was $26.50 \pm 2.78 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $28.75 \pm 2.92 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for male and female hostel respectively as compared to $25\text{-}30 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ recommended by WHO standard. This implies that, both the male and female;s borehole water are within the recommended limits. Similar finding reported in Choba campus university portharcourt Nigeria's borehole water by Ugwoha and Nwike, 2018. BOD showcased $4.88 \pm 10.27 \text{ mg/l}$ for male hostel and $10.75 \pm 1.39 \text{ mg/l}$ for female hostel as against to 5.0 mg/l set up by WHO recommendation limit. The study understood the level of BOD in the both hostels were above the WHO recommended limit, that might signified the presence of biological parameter and their detectability from the both borehole water. Turbidity in male hostel was $0.00 \pm 0.00 \text{ NTU}$ and that of the female hostel was $0.13 \pm 0.35 \text{ NTU}$ as opposed to 5.0 NTU recommended by the WHO. Different finding reported from N'Jamena Chad public school's borehole by Abdoulaye *et al.*, 2022, where it's recorded above the WHO recommended limit, the difference which might be as a results of one soil and or community specific factor or the orher. DO level in the male hostel was $7.63 \pm 15.60 \text{ mg/l}$, while that of the female hostel's borehole was $2.00 \pm 1.93 \text{ mg/l}$ as compared to that of both WHO standard ($5.0\text{-}10.0 \text{ mg/l}$). The study observed that, the DO level from the two hostels were below the WHO set up limit, the reason which suggested biological contamination as a results of the unsanitary habits of the students. TDS in male student hostel's borehole water sample was $0.55 \pm 1.40 \text{ mg/l}$, and that in the female hostel's borehole showed $0.88 \pm 1.73 \text{ mg/l}$ as compared to the WHO set up limit ($250\text{-}500 \text{ mg/l}$), so the TDS were below the recommended limit by the WHO guidelines. Similar finding reported by Odeyemi *et al.*, 2023 in Ado Ekiti, Nigeria. TSS concentration showed $0.90 \pm 0.84 \text{ mg/l}$ and $0.75 \pm 0.71 \text{ mg/l}$ for male and female hostel's borehole respectively in comparison to 1000 mg/l recommended by WHO. Hence the concentrations for the both hostels were below standard. The study contradicted the study reported from Borno state's borehole water by Musa *et al.*, 2023). The coliform detected in MPN index/100ml was 1.81 ± 0.18 and 2.21 ± 0.00 for male and female hostel's borehole respectively as compared to $0.00 \text{ MPN index/100ml}$ recommended by WHO standard. The coliform level in the two borehole sites were above permissible limit set up by WHO standard. This suggested that, the students mostly in the female hostel used to engage in unhygienic habit typically associated with illegal and controlled defecation. Coliform has been detected by many researchers in their borehole water being attributed to one factor or the other, the researchers such as Chad, in N'jameni city public schools by Abdoulaye *et al.*, 2022, from kwara state communities borehole by Abdulsalam and Sule, 2020, From Ado Ekiti's borehole water by Odeyemi *et al.*, 2023, with different case reported from Choba campus University boreholes by Ungwoha and Nwike, 2018, the variations which might be attributed to the student's or the communities hygienic status.

CONCLUSION

The male and female borehole water in Abdu Gusau polytechnic showcased versatility in the physicochemical and biological parameters as compared to the WHO set up limit as pH, EC, BOD, Turbidity and Temperature fall within the WHO recommended level. DO was above the WHO limit in the male hostel, but below the limit in the female hostel. The coliform level detected were above the WHO limit from the both male and the female hostel's borehole water. The water from the male hostel is

more pure and likely portable as compared to the water collected from the female hostel. However the water from the two borehole were not absolutely pure, hence do not conformed to WHO recommended standard. Therefore proper water treatments are to be applied before consuming the water.

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